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How do grant application criteria influence inequalities in research funding? ¹

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Introduction

Whether through interviews, metrics or lotteries, funders want to select grant proposals most likely to meet their objectives. Increasingly, funders recognise the importance of funding a diversity of individuals and approaches. Despite these efforts, gender inequalities in research funding remain observed. Previous research on gender inequalities has suggested various possible explanatory factors (Cruz-Castro & Sanz-Menéndez, 2020). Implicit bias on the part of reviewers may play a role, but evaluation criteria themselves may also affect such gender inequalities (Witteman et al., 2019). In the RoRI CRITERIA project, we examine gender differences in funding based on data of over 70,000 applications in 42 funding programmes from 9 funders² across the globe. Each programme uses different selection processes in different contexts. The aim of the project is to identify how grant evaluation criteria affect gender differences.

Methodology

We focused only on specific funding programmes. These funding programmes had to be (i) single applicants only (i.e. not including programmes with multiple PIs); (ii) should be focused on research (i.e. not travel or equipment); and (iii) open for general applications (i.e. no special

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² ARC, CIHR, India Alliance, Michael Smith Health Research BC, NNF, NWO, RCN, UKRI and Wellcome Trust.

topic calls). In addition, only funding programmes were included for which data quality could be sufficiently ensured by the funders providing the data. Each participating funder selected the programmes they deemed to fit this description best. In total, the 9 funders submitted 42 different programmes for analysis. Some funding programmes underwent changes during the period of analysis. For instance, RCN changed its Young Talents funding programme in 2020, no longer evaluating novelty and originality but emphasising broader societal impact instead. When programmes changed their criteria, these have been separately included in our analysis, in order to analyse how these changes relate to the gender differences in funding rates.

All funders submitted review material in order to determine the criteria that were used to evaluate grant proposals. This material includes call for proposals, application forms, reviewer instructions and forms, and other supporting information. Based on this material, we inductively established an ontology of criteria used for grant evaluation. We distinguish between five different domains: (A) the evaluation criteria; (B) the application process; (C) the eligibility criteria; (D) reviewer guidance and (E) grant conditions. The evaluation criteria are subdivided in three subdomains: (i) the programme of research; (ii) experience and track record; and (iii) contextual setting. This subdivision has a strong resemblance to the ontology created by (Hug & Aeschbach, 2020). The application process includes items such as whether there is an interview round or whether pre-proposals are required. The eligibility criteria includes criteria such as whether applicants must be in a certain career stage (e.g. 4 years after PhD). The reviewer guidance describes items such as whether certain training is being offered to reviewers. Finally, the grant conditions describe whether for instance funding can be held part-time or allows for parental leave. We provide a full overview of all criteria in Table 1.

Table 1. Evaluation criteria ontology for 42 programmes with indication of how many programmes are using a particular criteria.

Evaluation criteria		Process	
Program of Research		Pre-application	7
Originality of research question	37	Interview	16
Ambition of proposal	35	Open resubmissions allowed?	35
Strength of methodology	36	Funder diversity measures?	5
Resourcing	36		
High Risk included?	29	Eligibility	
Consideration of Ethical Issues	20	PI salary	26
Sex / Gender related aspects	2	Location	33
Potential for innovation and societal impact	21	Must have a clinical role	4
		Must be within x years of qualifying	17
Experience and track record		This grant can be awarded only once	29
Established research leader	18	Research falls into stated topic themes	18
Supervision, training and mentoring of others	15	Letter of recommendation?	26
Funding record	5		
Quality of previous work	36	Reviewer Guidance	
Innovative ideas	25	Unconscious bias training	17
Leadership potential	23	Responsible use of publications	17
Reputation and wider recognition	14	Mandatory reviewer training (diploma)	3
Use Bibliometrics	6	Policy regarding career break	29
Contextual setting		Grant conditions	
Research environment [Host] (REN)	35	Part time?	31
		Parental leave?	36

Some criteria were nearly universally implemented or used by all funding programmes included in this study. For instance, almost all funding programmes evaluate the originality, the ambition and the methodology of the research proposal. Other criteria were almost never included. For instance, only two funding programmes evaluated whether sex or gender was addressed in the research proposal when relevant, which is especially the case in a medical context (Sugimoto et al., 2019). Only few funding programmes seem to have mandatory reviewer training. There are also quite a number of criteria that are more divided. For instance, slightly less than half of the funding programmes evaluate established leadership qualities, and slightly more than half evaluate the potential societal impact of research proposals.

Although we coded all criteria in a dichotomous fashion, many criteria are implemented in a more nuanced and specific way. For instance, we have included a criterion in our ontology about whether open resubmissions after rejection are allowed or not. Most funders have specific rules, such as not being allowed to submit more than twice for a specific programme, not being allowed to submit two years in a row, or requiring substantial changes upon resubmission. We have also retained these more nuanced distinctions to inform our further analysis. We will not include the criteria directly in our statistical analysis, but rather, perform a qualitative analysis of the criteria after inferring the gender differences. If needed, we can also go back to the original review material for more in-depth information. The coding of all criteria have been reviewed by funders and where necessary changes were made.

We collected data of applications for each funding programme in two different tracks. One track included personal data, allowing us to link applications to bibliometric data sources. We have developed a dedicated funder data platform in order to facilitate the sharing of such personal data. By linking applications to bibliometric data sources, we can control for various bibliometric features in our statistical analysis, including the number of publications and their citation impact, academic age, the research field(s) of applicants, and their institutional affiliation. We call this the on-platform track. Unfortunately, not all funders were able to share personal data due to legal restrictions, and we therefore collected fully anonymous data in the other track, only providing aggregate funding statistics, but separately for different genders. We call this the off-platform track.

Our statistical analysis of gender differences is based on a simple hierarchical Bayesian model with weakly informative priors. Each application i takes place in a specific funding round r_i which is part of some funding programme p_i , and for each individual application i we know it is funded or not Y_i , and the gender g_i , for which we used the categories male, female, non-binary, prefer to self-describe and other. We are interested in whether different gender g_i have a different probability of being funded Y_i . We infer this using Bayesian logistic regression:

$$Y_i \sim \text{Bernoulli}(P_i)$$

$$P_i = \alpha_{p_i, r_i} + \beta_{p_i, r_i, g_i}$$

where $\alpha_{p,r}$ is the overall effect to be funded for round r of programme p and $\beta_{p,r,g}$ is the specific probability for gender g to get funded within some specific round r of funding programme p . Our interest is not in gender differences in any particular funding round. Instead, we are interested in the overall gender differences in the entire programme. We therefore use a hierarchical formulation that partially pools these estimates across the various funding rounds at the level of the overall programme:

$$\beta_{p,r,g} \sim \text{Normal}(\beta_{p,g}, \sigma_{p,g})$$

We only report results for this model. Results for the model that controls for various bibliometric features are work in progress.

Results

Although we infer effects for all genders, for most genders the sample size is rather small, and there are no clear effects visible. We therefore focus on the difference in funding rates between male and female applicants. We present results in terms of odds ratio of the funding rate of women over men over the entire programme, that is $\exp(\beta_{p,m})/\exp(\beta_{p,f})$. We typically report the full posterior distribution in figures, and present the 95% credibility interval in the text, sometimes accompanied by a median point estimate.

We first discuss the results for the off-platform track (Figure 1). Our results show that there is no strong evidence for gender differences in most programmes. Some programmes do show a larger difference, but this is typically in favour of women, not in favour of men. Only one program, the Australian Laureate Fellowships shows a consistently larger funding rate of women than of men (95% CI 0.46–0.95). The funding rate of women in the RCN Young Talent programme might have slightly increased after a change in the programme in 2020. Before 2020, the median odds ratio was 0.83 (95% CI 0.61–1.14), while after 2020 the odds ratio decreased to 0.59 (95% CI 0.30–1.47). The NWO programme also underwent a small change in 2018, requiring an institutional embedding guarantee, possibly slightly decreasing the funding rate of women from an odds ratio of 0.81 (95% CI 0.45–1.53) to 0.93 (95% CI 0.69–1.26). The UKRI AHRC Early Career fellowship shows a slightly higher funding rate of men (95% CI 0.50–1.32) than its Standard Route fellowships (95% CI 0.33–1.34). The CDA programme of the UKRI MRC is one of the few programmes that shows a higher funding rate of women than men with an odds ratio of 1.26 (95% CI 0.80–2.07). However, all mentioned differences are very small and show great uncertainty.

Figure 1. Posterior distribution of the odds ratio for programmes in the off-platform track.

The results for the on-platform track are largely similar (Figure 2), and show no strong evidence for gender differences in most programmes, and programmes with larger differences typically

tend towards funding women at higher rates. India Alliance tends to fund women more in its CPH Early Career fellowship (95% CI 0.24–1.03). The NNF POC program also shows larger funding rates for women (95% CI 0.24–1.31).

Figure 2. Posterior distribution of the odds ratio for programmes in the on-platform track.

Discussion

Diversity, equality and fairness in funding is of great concern to many funders. We here analysed gender differences in the funding rates across several funders and funding programmes. We found no strong evidence of any gender differences. Moreover, we would like to emphasise that observed gender differences in funding cannot be interpreted as evidence of *gender bias*, understood as a direct causal effect, in the evaluation of grant applications. Observing no gender differences makes it perhaps less plausible that some gender bias is at play, but this cannot be ruled out. In particular, earlier gender biases (e.g. in hiring or promotion) may affect outcomes such that the gender bias in funding is masked.

There is some variability in gender differences in funding programmes. Some funding programmes changed during the time of analysis, which we compared to the evaluation criteria being used by the different programmes. Possibly, these criteria may increase the funding rate of women: having some diversity policy; not having an interview stage; evaluating leadership potential instead of established leadership; not considering historical funding track records; not asking for letters of recommendations. However, all differences are very small and very uncertain, and the effect of (not) having these criteria on gender differences is very uncertain.

There are still clear gender differences in the science system, with women being less represented among researchers in most fields (Boekhout et al., 2021). Research funding plays a large role in academic careers and outcomes, and funders should analyse the outcomes of their funding process to monitor their effects. Our results show that research funding does not show gender differences and therefore does not seem to contribute to the overall gender difference in

the science system. Efforts to improve the representation of women in science may therefore perhaps be better focused elsewhere in the science system.

References

- Boekhout, H., van der Weijden, I., & Waltman, L. (2021). Gender differences in scientific careers: A large-scale bibliometric analysis. In *arXiv [cs.DL]*. arXiv. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2106.12624>
- Bol, T., de Vaan, M., & van de Rijt, A. (2022). Gender-equal funding rates conceal unequal evaluations. *Research Policy*, *51*(1), 104399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104399>
- Cruz-Castro, L., & Sanz-Menéndez, L. (2020). *Grant Allocation Disparities from a Gender Perspective: Literature Review. Synthesis Report.* GRANteD Project. <https://doi.org/10.20350/digitalCSIC/10548>
- Hug, S. E., & Aeschbach, M. (2020). Criteria for assessing grant applications: a systematic review. *Palgrave Communications*, *6*(1), 37. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-0412-9>
- Sugimoto, C. R., Ahn, Y.-Y., Smith, E., Macaluso, B., & Larivière, V. (2019). Factors affecting sex-related reporting in medical research: a cross-disciplinary bibliometric analysis. *The Lancet*, *393*(10171), 550–559. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)32995-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)32995-7)
- Witteman, H. O., Hendricks, M., Straus, S., & Tannenbaum, C. (2019). Are gender gaps due to evaluations of the applicant or the science? A natural experiment at a national funding agency. *The Lancet*, *393*(10171), 531–540. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)32611-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)32611-4)